

CROSS-CUTTING WORK WITH ALL CHARTER WPS TO DEVELOP ARCTIC STRATEGY AND PROVIDE POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

CHARTER deliverable 6.5

Grant Agreement Number: 869471

Project Acronym: CHARTER

Project title: Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic
Terrestrial Biodiversity

Starting Date: 01/08/2020

Project Duration: 54 months

Project Officer: Alberto Zocchi

Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

Leading Authors: Jussi Eronen, Sirpa Rasmus, Simo
Sarkki (UH, LAY)

Contributing partners: NINA, UmU, UHAM, AWI

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DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	
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CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. the Commission services)	

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10.1.2025	Jussi Eronen, Sirpa Rasmus, Simo Sarkki, Bruce Forbes	Additions after last CHARTER events
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Introduction

This deliverable reports the work carried out in CHARTER task 6.5: “Work together with cross-cutting themes and WP7 to help with decision-maker interaction and developing Arctic strategy”. The work has been led by WP6 and University of Helsinki, with strong support from WPs 3, 5 and 7 and from various partners, especially UHAM, UmU, NINA and UZH (workshops), AWI (climate scenario work), NMBU, UEF and UiT (help with material and background). All CHARTER partners have contributed to the development of narrative scenarios and policy options/recommendations, through earlier WP6 publications, targeted sessions during CHARTER annual meetings, and commenting our drafts. The collaboration between WP6 and WP7 has been especially related to dissemination material and organizing events. Part of this has been, collaborating with other Horizon -funded projects ECOTIP and FACE-IT, though joint policy briefs.

Work in task 6.5 has been organizing workshops, townhall events and world cafés for discussion and dissemination, and writing perspective -papers and other scientific publications. The work has both gathered information needed to produce pathway narratives and policy options (D6.4) and to discuss and communicate these, both in events listed in this document, and as openly available visual outputs (<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/95207a47d7bf4d5bb674a66da6a3db79>).

CHARTER has fostered the open dialogue on Arctic topics in various ways. We have aimed at co-design approach – working together on land-use and biodiversity narrative scenarios and related policy options with stakeholders – decision-makers and others. Co-production of knowledge in participatory workshops has been important part of this work.

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Most of the workshops were aimed at practical level – individual, family and herding community level. Participants were also from the administrative or governance level, as well as other land-users/stakeholders. Workshops especially targeted to decision-makers or planners were organized in Savukoski (municipality leaders) and for the Reindeer Herders Association board members. Workshops organized in all three Nordic countries in late summer – autumn 2023 had elements of supporting dialogue between local level and national governance level, as well as supporting interactions with stakeholders.

Towards the end of the project topics have been discussed and scenarios / policy options presented in common learning events such as world cafés, and town hall events. In this report we list these events, from June 2024 to January 2025, with their outcomes and next steps.

Earlier workshops

Participatory workshops have been organized by WPs 3 and 6 with local practitioners of nature-based livelihoods, especially reindeer herders and stakeholders in reindeer husbandry. These have been important parts of the research process and reported in deliverables D3.3 (from August 2021 to August 2022, 11 events in Finland and in Sweden) and D3.7 (from August 2022 to November 2023, nine events in Finland, Norway and Sweden). The work has also been reflected by several researchers in deliverables D3.6 (“Summary of CHARTER WP3 field research: data collection, metadata, key findings”), in D3.11 (“Futures of reindeer herding”) and in the WP3 synthesis, D3.8.

Many of the workshops summarized earlier, and also work described here, have been organized jointly with other EU Horizon -funded projects ECOTIP, FACE-IT, ArcticHubs and/or JUSTNORTH, or in collaboration with other international and national projects, notably: AROSS (<https://nsidc.org/rain-on-snow>), NKJ Network (<https://nordicagriresearch.org/2021-02/>), CLIMINI (<https://www.arcticcentre.org/FI/climini/climini-EN>), POVAUS (<https://www.luke.fi/en/projects/povaus>), SUURPORO (<https://www.luke.fi/en/projects/suurporo-01>), POMURI (<https://www.luke.fi/en/projects/pomuri>).

Of the workshops already listed and summarized, the most important ones in the view of task 6.5 have been the futures workshop for the board members of the Reindeer Herders' Association of Finland, 9.12.2022, in Rovaniemi, Finland (with participants discussing on path forward in reindeer husbandry, and how the RHA

can support it), the futures workshop in the municipality of Savukoski, 13 April 2023, in Savukoski, Finland (with municipality representatives participating, and discussions had on municipality strategy), and the “second part” of the futures workshop had for actors in reindeer husbandry, 13.11.2023, in Rovaniemi, Finland (where participants worked on the difficult topic of implementation – how the next steps could be taken, so that aims and dreams listed in reindeer husbandry could even tried to be achieved. See Figure 1. As this part of the work was close collaboration with national project POVAUS, workshop is summarized also in the final report of that project (Pekkarinen & Rasmus, 2024).

Figure 1. Reindeer husbandry actors were invited to a workshop titled “Dreams and surprises, Vol II” that was held in connection to the Arctic Spirit conference in Rovaniemi, Finland, in November 2023, in collaboration with project POVAUS. Photos: Sirpa Rasmus.

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Earlier policy events

Policy events have been organized together with other EU Horizon -funded projects. One of the most important ones was the “mid-term policy event” – a joint policy briefing of CHARTER, ECOTIP and FACE-IT, titled “Arctic biodiversity, climate and food security. The event was organized at the EU Commission's department for Research and Innovation in Brussels on 15.3.2023. It was attended by 40 people and was chaired by Dr. Renuka Badhe, Executive Secretary of the European Polar Board. More about event here: <https://www.charter-arctic.org/report-on-arctic-biodiversity-climate-and-food-security-in-brussels-with-webstream-and-photos/> Briefing material is also available for example here: <https://zenodo.org/records/7762347#.ZBwFmMKZNhk>. These recommendations are relevant to strategies being developed by the European Union and other international organisations in relation to the climate change and biodiversity crises. More specifically, for the EU's Arctic policy, EU missions and the Green Deal, as well as the work of IPCC and IPBES. Continuation of this collaboration was the creation of joint fact-sheets: synthesis of research results, and joint view on research priorities and research gaps (<https://www.charter-arctic.org/charter-fact-sheets/>). These fact-sheets have been presented for example at the EU Arctic Forum and Indigenous Peoples' Dialogue, in Brussels 14.-15.5.2024.

Another example was presenting CHARTER and its future-oriented work during an international and high-level “learning visit”, 24.2.2023 in Rovaniemi, Finland, organized by project JUSTNORTH. In this event for example personnel from The Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions, DG Mare, and European External Action Service participated.

Earlier researcher panels, workshops, world cafes

ActicHubs, CHARTER and JUSTNORTH organized a world-café type of joint event during the Arctic Frontiers conference in Tromsø, Norway, on 1.2.2023. This collaborative event titled “Land use, reconciliation and justice in the Arctic” was organized at the Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture Research (NOFIMA). Research findings and experiences across the three projects were shared, and views around environmental change, land use policies and Arctic futures collected together. The event was attended by approximately 25 project members and collaborators, also one representative from the project Arctic PASSION. At the centre of group discussions were the legacies of past harms and injustices and what existing legacies of development we can still see in the

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landscape. We also discussed what are the biggest threats for the Arctic, what green transition really means, re-development of post-industrial places, about the changing ecosystems and needs for adaptation, brainstorming what win-win solutions could be available. We ended the workshop on dreaming about the future of the Arctic which would look more inclusive, sustainable with stable ecosystems and white winters where tourists could contribute on positive development.

ArcticHubs, CHARTER and JUSTNORTH have collaborated also to organize joint sessions and panel discussion on Arctic land-use related issues as part of Arctic Spirit conferences, Rovaniemi, Finland, in November 2021 and in November 2023 (titled "Arctic landscapes under pressure - effects of national and international policies and businesses on land-use development"). CHARTER, ECOTIP, and FACE-IT lead scientists have participated in various high-level panels – jointly or representing the group of projects. One example is the Arctic Science Summit Week 2024 (Edinburgh, Scotland from 21.3. to 29.3.2024), where Bruce Forbes, CHARTER PI, discussed in a panel titled "Making an inclusive and holistic Arctic Observing system through inclusion of diverse knowledge systems - how to progress?"

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Events and their take-home messages, June 2024 – January 2025

"Resilient futures of Arctic livelihoods" – world café at SRI, June 2024

Together with ArcticHubs, a joint world café -type of session was organized on 10.6.2024 in Espoo, Finland, as part of the Sustainability Research & Innovation Congress that was held in Espoo/Helsinki, Finland, in June 2024. The SRI congress was linked to annual Sustainability Science Days. The session was titled "Resilient futures of Arctic livelihoods", and it was attended by approximately 20 people with diverse backgrounds. The session consisted of introductory presentations by project representatives and the Ministry of the Environment in Finland, followed by world café discussions on "good futures" for three livelihoods in the Arctic: forestry, reindeer husbandry and tourism. For example, the "good future" for reindeer husbandry was considered to consist of these core elements, raising from CHARTER participatory work: good ecological state of seasonal pastures, connectedness, accessibility of pastures; grazing peace (not too much infra, roads, tourists, predators etc.); better governance and land-use decision-making. Three groups discussed what do these dreams and aims could mean in practice, and what could be next steps towards these. Finally, win-wins and synergies were discussed together: were there common topics, and potential developments that could benefit all three livelihoods considered. Combining traditional knowledge and new innovations, developing multifunctionality of landscapes, and getting bottom-up view to the decision-making were mentioned.

"Making more inclusive forecasting products" – workshop at EFI, June 2024

Key researchers from WP5 and WP6 were invited to attend the researcher workshop "How do we make more inclusive products in ecological forecasting?" which was organized on 12.6.2024, during the Ecological Forecasting Initiative conference held in Helsinki, Finland. Approximately 20 researchers attended this workshop. We presented the transdisciplinary work towards locally relevant climate model outputs, and more generally, discussed on the future-oriented work and tools developed in CHARTER to support it.

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“Building pathways towards desirable futures for Arctic biodiversity” workshop at WBF, June 2024

CHARTER partner University of Zurich (Jakob J. Assmann and Gabriela Schaeppman-Strub as main organizers), together with consultancy company Oliver Wyman (London), planned and ran the design thinking workshop titled “Building pathways towards desirable futures for Arctic biodiversity”, as part of the World Biodiversity Forum 2024 in Davos, Switzerland, in June 2024. The workshop planning was motivated by the IPBES Nature Futures Framework for developing desirable futures (<https://www.ipbes.net/scenarios-models>) and ongoing research in CHARTER, FACE-IT and ECOTIP projects. Several CHARTER WP6 researchers were part of the planning group for the event. Scientists, practitioners, Indigenous right- and stakeholders, policy makers and people from all backgrounds with an interest in the topic were invited to share their knowledge and think about biodiversity in the Arctic of the future. The workshop was attended by several tens of WBF participants, with diverse backgrounds - including members of CHARTER project (on terrestrial biodiversity) and FACE-IT project (on coastal biodiversity). WBZ was held on 16.-21.6.2024, with a general theme “From science to action”. The workshop was organized on 16.6.2024. Workshop description here: <https://wbf2024.abstractserver.com/program/#/details/sessions/172>.

First the Nature Futures Framework and some case studies were presented, followed by facilitated workshop discussions. What do we mean by positive future outlook in the Arctic - how would that future look like and what sort of concrete examples we could give? Important themes to consider were food security, economy-infrastructure-biodiversity nexus, Arctic model for governance with biodiversity, co-managing thriving Arctic ecosystems, and biodiversity-climate interactions. For all themes, important points listed were locally-led solutions, education and outreach, empowering Arctic decision-making, need for open monitoring and knowledge sharing, managing conflict and diverse views, and adaptability. The group made some commitments: to stay open and focus on those who also are, to develop primary school education initiative, to highlight the opportunities for positive futures, to de-colonize research; to integrate Indigenous perspectives into all Arctic research; to continue learning about Arctic biodiversity, and to continue to collaborate with colleagues met, and the dialogue.

Participants reported that their outlook on Arctic biodiversity future had shifted towards the positive due to workshop discussions - and that is a key for action, as well. Graphical output was produced during the workshop (Figure 2), and findings are being synthesized in an opinion piece. Summary video by Oliver Wyman here: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7209459215910719488/>

Figure 2. Graphical outcomes of the Arctic Biodiversity Futures - workshop at the World Biodiversity Forum in Davos, Switzerland, June 2024. Content generated by all workshop participants and captured by artist Ollie Prothero from Oliver Wyman. Photos: Irina Wang.

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Nordic workshop at Reindeer and fish research days, August 2024

CHARTER organized its last participatory workshop in northern Finland in August 2024. Workshop was organized in Ylläs, 26.-27.8.2025, linked to “Reindeer and Fish research days” also arranged there (27.-28.8.2024). After several workshops had been held in Finland, Norway and Sweden, a joint event was planned to bring together some herders and researchers around a shared workshop table. The aim was to have a small workshop, with people comfortable working in English – this time we wanted to avoid the hassle of translations back and forth. We had altogether ten participants in the workshop, six of these herders coming from different herding districts or samebys from Finland, Norway and Sweden – both from Sápmi, and from regions more south. Researchers facilitating the workshop were Tim Horstkotte, Sirpa Rasmus and Jussi Eronen (CHARTER) and Stefan Sandström (LANDPATHS; <https://landpaths.blog.uu.se/en/home/>). These researchers with long experience on workshop topic also took part for some time: Mikko Jokinen (Natural Resources Institute, Finland); Otto Habeck (University of Hamburg, Germany), Bruce Forbes (University of Lapland, Finland), Svein Morten Eilertsen (Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research).

Most of the participants had attended one or more future-oriented workshops organized by CHARTER researchers earlier, in one of the countries. In these, both presentations, discussions, mappings, and “game methods” had been used. Mixed methods were used also in Ylläs. Herders had time to present their district, timely issues and pressures and open questions (Figure 3). A pilot version of a new “Herding game” was also used to facilitate the discussions (Figure 4; see the Appendix I). The idea was to continue the discussions had in earlier workshops, so main issues were ongoing developments in land-use and in climate. Coping, adapting and thriving, also in difficult situations, were discussed. The theme of the research days was “Integration of traditional knowledge and scientific knowledge - why, how, and for whom?”. Because of this, knowledge was also an important part of our workshop discussions (acknowledging and utilizing different knowledges; including Indigenous and local knowledge in decision making, mapping and understanding the various knowledge sources that could be used, when difficulties arise in reindeer herding; what do others need to understand about districts, and herding, in difficult situations created by different drivers; when impact assessments are made in land-use projects, what are the factors and topics that need to be considered so that the assessment truly reflects reindeer herders’ viewpoints; consequences of competing knowledge or lack of knowledge).

The first day was dedicated to discussions about local urgent issues, and trying the first version of a “Herding game” that is under development. The game is a tool to

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facilitate discussions about reactions to and resources needed in different seasonal circumstances – to share and explain different needs and possibilities more easily than when “just” talking. The idea is also to show cumulative impacts of consecutive seasons in a concrete way – and enable adding various, locally relevant “surprises”, like rapid land-use developments, into discussions without forgetting the biophysical environment and its variability.

We especially discussed different difficult seasonal weather events, how these were experienced in district and samebys represented, and what sort of resources could be used to “play the cards right” and live well through the year – until the next calving season. Because of the theme, “knowledge”, discussions emphasized the knowledge base of decisions made, and also knowledge that may be lacking in some cases – be it traditional knowledge, scientific knowledge and monitoring, or knowledge possessed by other land-users and people working in the governance or administration. We talked a lot about passing the knowledge on to new generations and language issues, about new knowledge formed in new situations, and because of the use of new technology like drones, and the localized nature of knowledge.

After discussing compounding impacts of consecutive weather events during seasons, we also continued by adding a “surprise” card, which said wolves. This meant discussing the impact of predation during certain seasonal (possibly difficult) conditions. In a same way, impacts of other pressures, like land-use development within seasonal pasture area, or infrastructure development through herding district, could be added to the discussions had during the game. This way practical examples of rather vague concept of “cumulative impacts” could be introduced and explained in concrete way to other “players”, for example people living outside of reindeer management area, or people students, or people working in the administrative level of the livelihood.

This was one of the first tries with the game, and participants shared our view that this tool could be developed into something that could help also the governance level, and other land-users, to understand the herder point of view better, and enable discussions related to resources, well-targeted support from the governance side, and seasonal impacts of land-use.

Figure 3: Presenting local cases (photos J. Eronen).

Figure 4: Playing the “Herding game” (photos J. Eronen). Pay attention to the color of “reaction tokens” and resources used per season.

The second day of the workshop started with following the NKJ-organized panel, with a focus on different knowledge systems (Figure 5): <https://nordicagriresearch.org/news/panel-debate-different-knowledge-systems-and-their-marks-on-reindeer-husbandry/>. Sirpa Rasmus and Sofie Andersson facilitated the discussion, panelists being Marja-Kristin Skum (herder in Gran Sameby, Sweden, and secretary at the Truth Commission for the Sami people in Sweden), Svein Morten Eilertsen (research scientist at NIBIO, Division of Forest and Forest Resources Wildlife and Rangelands in Norway), Sanna Hast (land-use specialist at the Reindeer Herders' Association in Finland) and Bruce Forbes (research professor at the Arctic Centre, University of Lapland, Finland; CHARTER PI). The panel presented several interesting viewpoints and recent developments related to the integrating herders' local knowledge in research and in impact assessments, and also raised many open questions – questions and critical points were also made by the audience, for example mentioning the participation fatigue, need to compensate local peoples' time when participating in processes, and needs and possibilities for cross-border collaboration.

Figure 5: Panel on different knowledge systems; the discussion was streamed and recorded; one of the panelists participated online. Several of our workshop participants actively commented the panel discussion (photos S. Rasmus)

Workshop discussions were continued after the panel, trying to illustrate what “cumulative impacts” mean at local level, when considering weather conditions, land-use conflicts, and perhaps also shortcomings in the governance (regulations, legislation and planning; compensations; subsidies) all together. What knowledge is needed in different cases – and resources like trust? Discussions emphasized especially local impacts of tourism, and experiences on hunting with dogs. Assessing

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the cumulative impacts need to be developed further – and in these assessments, impacts of past developments, cumulated during decades, need to be taken into account. The past should not be forgotten. Another thing that should be more visible in national legislation and governance of the livelihood is the local decision-making and land management systems (in Sámi herding tradition this means the siida system). Poor understanding on this means that local impacts of land encroachments are not fully understood, either.

Discussions revealed differences and similarities between districts and countries – and the feeling that even though the livelihood is hard, people want to continue herding - it is part of the identity. More cross-border dialogue was hoped for, and continuation for processes started. The next opportunity for researcher-herder dialogue will be in Alta, northern Norway, in February 2025, during the Nordic Conference on Reindeer Husbandry Research (<https://nibio.pameldingssystem.no/reindriftskonferansen-2025>).

“Arctic biodiversity at a crossroad” session at European Polar Science week, September 2024

Several CHARTER project researchers attended the European Polar Science week (3.-6.9.2024). in Copenhagen organised by the European Commission and the European Space Agency. CHARTER, ECOTIP and FACE-IT organized a joint session with talks and a panel on 5.9.2024, titled “Arctic biodiversity at a crossroads - Research directions along the land-coast-ocean continuum” (<https://www.charter-arctic.org/charter-at-european-polar-science-week/>). CHARTER findings and results were presented by Mariana García Criado (UEDIN) in this well attended session. This was an excellent opportunity to tell the wider scientific community and EU policy makers about the results that CHARTER has developed and what research gaps remain.

OECD briefing, Rovaniemi, September 2024

The OECD delegation preparing a country report about Finland from economy perspective visited Rovaniemi, northern Finland on 19.9.2024. Together with other Arctic research projects, CHARTER was presented, and key findings discussed with the delegation in a small event organized at Arctic Centre.

CHARTER final meeting, Rovaniemi, November 2024

Even though not planned as such, the final meeting of CHARTER (Rovaniemi, Finland, 12.-14.11.2024) was a place for outreach – and dialogue – itself, with more than 70 researchers and collaborators spending three intensive days together (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Encounters with collaborators during CHARTER final meeting; Pavel Tkach (LAY, Arctic PASSION), Enni Similä (Sámi Council, ReCap ASáp), Teresa Komu (OU), Juhani Lakela (Kemin-Sompio herding district) and Tim Horstkotte (UmU) in the panel.

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“Arctic future pathways” - Townhall event in Helsinki, January 2025

As its last policy event, CHARTER organized an “Arctic afternoon” in Helsinki, Finland, on 8.1.2025. This was planned and carried out as a collaboration between WPs 6 and 7 – University of Lapland researchers and science communication, and researchers from universities of Helsinki and Jyväskylä. The event was targeted to policymakers, decision makers and others working on (or interested in) Arctic issues in Helsinki. Approximately 30 people attended: many from ministries or other governance/administration institutions. The aim was to bring “the discussion about North” to Helsinki, with northern people actually having the discussion on issues important to them.

After Markku Heikkilä (LAY) had opened the event, Jussi Eronen (UH) and Sirpa Rasmus (LAY) presented shortly the CHARTER policy brief titled “Tensional dreams: Policy Options for a Sustainable Arctic”, the future-oriented work done during CHARTER years, and the general setting in northern Fennoscandia that can be called as polycrisis. Rapidly advancing climate change and related ecosystem changes, significant land-use pressures, impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the current tensional geopolitical situation are all something to cope with, and take into account when hopeful, locally desirable futures are discussed (yes, hopeful views on future are still allowed!). After this Johanna Yletyinen (JyU) presented work on social influence related to northern land-use – who is impacting whom.

After researcher talks, four concrete examples or viewpoints from the environmental governance and northern livelihoods and communities were presented. **Leo Aikio (Sámi parliament)** asked who is using the voice of those, who do not have voice on their own – northern animals and fish, for example? And if someone speaks for these northern inhabitants, is someone listening and actually willing to change the way of life, so that also northern nature will have easier future? **Lotta Manninen (Ministry of Environment)** presented recent developments in the use of Indigenous knowledge as part of biodiversity related assessments, nature conservation, and natural resource management. **Sanna Hast (Reindeer Herders' Association)** asked is reindeer husbandry part of a problem, or part of a solution, when we think about sustainability transition in the future. Are herders slowing down good and necessary development? Why they are so often against land-use projects? Perhaps the presence of reindeer and livelihood-related infrastructure can also help to conserve old forest patches, and open fjell environment? Also, nature restoration projects can support both reindeer livelihood and biodiversity. **Jari Huotari (head of the municipal council, Inari)** talked about balancing act at the municipality level – how to plan and guide land use, when so

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many interests and needs are meeting. He emphasized early discussions among people, openness, and understanding of various needs.

Comments were given by Hannele Pokka (UH, with a long experience of decision making in the North and for the North); she reminded that northern areas can seem like empty, but they are not, every hectare is used by someone or for something – and emphasized the importance of municipality level decision making - and Johanna Ikävalko (AC), emphasizing the importance of national Arctic strategy (at poor state at the moment) and the need for scientific knowledge during the rapid change.

Last part of the event was a panel discussion moderated by Markku and Sirpa. Panelists were Sanna Hast, Leo Aikio and Jari Huotari, joined by Hilppa Gregow from Finnish meteorological institute (expert in climate change, also part of the new Sámi climate panel in Finland).

Several talks had presented examples of land use, need for holistic land-use governance, and meeting around a shared planning table with equal opportunities to impact. Is this possible? Willingness towards collaboration has increased. But how to get from talking to action? What would be needed, is understanding the functions and functionality of land areas. This means that knowledge of those practicing their livelihood within that landscape is needed. In land-use planning, issues often cross municipality borders, this is important to acknowledge. And more economical know-how is needed!

Many developments in the North are based on human decisions. But then there are developments like rapidly advancing climate change. What does adaptation mean for panelist? Is there room to adapt – is adaptation capacity depending on land-use? Leaders of states need to understand that mitigating the climate change is the key – then all other important issues can be addressed. There was agreement but also the feeling that while mitigating the climate change is needed, several other issues need to be solved, at the same time. Adaptation is a process, it never gets completely done. Often it is also incremental and reactive – there is no time and energy to think about solutions that could help more generally, in many different difficulties. Where is the capacity, and those who can work towards adaptation – how to respond to something, that has not been experienced before? The task to plan adaptation (at livelihood level) is urgent!

Knowledge is important part of adaptive capacity / resilience. Are multiple ways of knowing used in decision making (local knowledge, scientific knowledge, etc.). Are they trusted? Are decisions made so that they are based on knowledge, or perceptions or values? Decisions are based on knowledge, and also on values –

choosing what knowledge to use, that is also a value question. In the north, practical decisions are often based on traditional knowledge. But now, when changes are so rapid, traditional knowledge cannot be trusted like before. More generally, different ways of knowing need to be recognized, as part of valid knowledge base, in decision making processes. Perhaps educating the officials is a good step forward.

What is needed, to have a thriving North? Negotiations at municipality level, and trying to impact the regional, national, EU level decision making. Mitigating climate change. This requires a transition in the attitude and action. In a long run, thriving could be possible also in a very different climate, but that means also new knowledge and new traditions, and it takes several generations to create those. Thriving needs solutions that have been developed locally, based on local point of view. More encounters, dialogue, trust. Finding common ground: what do we mean when we talk using certain words – simple things. Understanding who listens when you speak, and where and to who you should speak, to make the impact. What are the avenues for interaction and communication.

The day finished with questions and discussion from the audience, and with a wish to continue dialogue either in Helsinki, or governance people invited to some northern location – or perhaps both? See also: <https://www.charter-arctic.org/arctic-future-pathways-charter-policy-event-held-in-helsinki/>.

Figure 7. Panel during the policy event in Helsinki, 8.1.2025

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Data and publications

Task 6.5 has produced places for dialogue and social learning, workshop summaries, reports and working papers. Work has been synthesized in a policy brief and its background documents (D6.4), and in joint policy briefs and “Knowledge gaps – recommendations” publications together with parallel EU Horizon -funded projects ECOTIP and FACE-IT. Scientific papers (original research, perspective/forum pieces) have been published, and more are being worked on (see table 1).

Original research data consists mainly of detailed notes and photos taken during workshops and other events. Because of the nature of the data, it is not shared openly. According to CHARTER data management plan, social and human science research data (including data produced in workshops) will be made as open as possible, but kept as closed as necessary. The principle of “Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC) has been used when gathering data. Using, re-using and sharing the data has been discussed with research partners. In practice, access to certain information will be kept limited. According to the FPIC by workshop participants, anonymized summaries can be published (as well as photos), but detailed (non-anonymised) research notes not. Summaries of discussions have been presented in this report and in earlier WP3 deliverables (most workshops have been organized as joint WP3-6 activities). Related to the content of detailed notes, for future research purposes, data creator can be contacted. Metadata table in the Appendix II gives needed details. Table 1 below links events to publications, which have used and reported workshop data (policy events, panels and the workshop organized during the World Biodiversity Forum not listed).

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Table 1. CHARTER WP6 activities (thematically grouped; policy events not listed) and resulted publications by CHARTER and collaborating projects. More details: metadata (Appendix II).

Workshops and other events	Reports, publications
<u>Emphasis on climate and weather:</u> -Workshop, Kuusamo, Finland, 24.8.2021 -Workshops, Inari, Finland, 5.5.2022 and 9.6.2022 -Workshop, Rovaniemi, Finland, 30.8.2023 -Workshop, Helsinki, Finland, 12.6.2024	Laptander et al. 2023 Matthes et al. (manuscript) Rasmus & Laptander (manuscript)
<u>Emphasis on female herders:</u> -Workshop, Rovaniemi, Finland, 15.9.2021 -Workshop, Inari, Finland, 3.5.2022 -Workshop, Kuusamo, Finland, 12.9.2022	Rasmus et al. 2022 Turunen et al. (submitted)
<u>Emphasis on winter feeding of reindeer:</u> -Workshop, Inari, Finland, 30.3.2022 -Workshop, Arvidsjaur, Sweden, 8.-9.6.2022	Skarin et al. 2024 (NKJ)-network publication)
<u>Emphasis on operational environment of reindeer husbandry, adaptation and future views (Surprises and dreams -workshops):</u> -Pilot workshop, Rovaniemi, Finland (Lapland University of Applied Sciences) 1.4.2022 -Pilot workshop, Inari, Finland (The Sámi Education Institute), 5.5.2022 -Townhall meeting (collecting input for workshops), Rovaniemi, Finland, 6.6.2022 -Workshop, Inari, Finland, 25.8.2022 -Workshop, Rovaniemi, Finland. 9.12.2022 -Three workshops in Jokkmokk, Sweden, 14.-17.8.2023 -Workshop in Rovaniemi, Finland 13.11.2023	Rasmus et al. 2023a; b Wang et al. 2023 Pekkarinen & Rasmus, 2024 (POVAUS -project publication) Rasmus et al. 2024 Sarkki, S & Rasmus et al. (submitted) Sarkki et al. a; b (submitted) Rasmus & Sarkki et al. (manuscript)
<u>Emphasis on pasture conditions:</u> -Workshop in Røros, Norway, 16.8.2023	Tømmervik 2023
<u>Emphasis on municipality level perceptions:</u> -Townhall meeting, 6.4.2022, Savukoski, Finland -Workshop, 13.4.2023, Savukoski, Finland	Eilola et al. 2024
<u>Emphasis on cumulative impacts and land-use:</u> -World café, Tromsø, Norway, 1.2.2023 -World café, Espoo, Finland, 10.6.2024 -Workshop in Ylläs, Finland, 26.-27.8.2024	Sarkki et al. 2023 CHARTER-project, 2024 Eronen et al. 2024 Sarkki et al. a; b (submitted)

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Conclusions and way forwards

WP6 has fruitfully supported the cross-cutting themes in CHARTER: “Tools and data for Arctic Strategies”, and “Public dialogue on the Arctic”. “Tools and data” include several publications, briefs and working papers, the “Surprises and dreams” - method (<https://zenodo.org/records/10038003>) has proved out to be a versatile tool to facilitate discussions, and used already by others than us, as well. Also, “the herding game” is worth developing further (for example, by developing different seasonal condition card decks for present day and future climates, and so on).

We have worked to maximize the impact of CHARTER through policy briefs and background papers (<https://www.charter-arctic.org/policy-briefs/>) and events explaining these, scientific papers relevant for decision making, outreach, and direct interaction with people making decisions. These have been some means CHARTER has used to participate in public dialogue on Arctic.

Activities have generally served our exploitation goals, although some stakeholders (like other land-users than herders) have been met less than hoped for, and it would have been useful to have more interaction with decision-makers. Discussions in CHARTER final meeting emphasized the importance of genuine and impactful links to decision making. We have done our best to get into dialogue on our research topics, both at EU-level and national/regional level in northern Fennoscandia, and can also show some successes, in this respect. Nevertheless, there is a feeling that more could have been done – and more needs to be done, in future projects. Our colleagues from other Horizon-projects and local collaborators emphasized the importance of “being there” for long enough and building trust, also with policymakers. Local (municipality level) contacts were mentioned. These lessons we will take to our future projects.

Workshops organized by CHARTER WPs 3 and 6 have served our work towards policy recommendations on sustainable Arctic. This involves taking into account aims and dreams at local level, not “only” EU and national-level sustainability interpretations and targets. Our work in WPs 3, 6 and 7 has been designed from the beginning of the project in co-productive fashion. This has also meant that many times the workshops have not had a clear agenda when started. We have spent a lot of time in each workshop and between events and workshops on discussing with stakeholders and participants on what are issues that are important to them, how we should organize events and what outcomes would be most fruitful for local, regional and state level actors. This has included many discussions on difficult

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topics, constant social learning, and many surprises. In all our work we have aimed for capacity building.

Two main themes that have emerged time and again in discussions and workshops are: land-use related decision-making, and preparation for current and future uncertainty. For the land-use decisions one of the key insights that we have gained is that even within the sustainable future trajectory there are multiple different paths that can be taken, and the choice which is taken will influence the land-use in the Arctic region a lot. This will involve decisions on whose voice will be heard and how, and who can develop the land and how (or not). The preparation for the uncertainty involves better understanding the changes happening now, and building resilience. The ongoing discussion is currently “resilience against what, for whom, and how”. This is something that needs much more work and research in the future.

Based on the workshops and other activities, WP6 has outlined strategies for long term maintenance of biodiversity and Arctic livelihoods, including policy recommendations. These have been outlined in our previous deliverable D6.4.

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References

CHARTER-project. 2024. TENSIONAL DREAMS: Policy Options for a Sustainable Arctic. CHARTER WP6 team. https://www.charter-arctic.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/CHARTER_PolicyBriefing_v8-DIGITAL.pdf

Eilola, S., Horstkotte, T., Forbes, B.C., Habeck, J.O. Komu, T., Rasmus, S., Fagerholm, N. 2024. Perceptions and impacts of environmental changes under multiple stressors: a case study from two boreal forest communities in northern Scandinavia/subarctic Scandinavia. *Regional Environmental Change* 24:89. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-024-02241-4>

Eronen, J., Rasmus, S. Sarkki, S. 2024. Tensional dreams – Policy option for a sustainable Arctic – Background for the policy brief. CHARTER working paper 4 https://www.charter-arctic.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/CHARTER_working_paper_4_tensional_dreams.pdf <https://septentrio.uit.no/index.php/rangifer/issue/view/732>

Laptander, R., Horstkotte, T., Habeck, J.O., <Rasmus, S., Komu, T., Matthes, H., Forbes, B.C., Istomin, K., Eronen, J.T. 2023. Critical Seasonal Conditions in the Reindeer-Herding Year: A Synopsis of Factors and Events in Fennoscandia and Northwestern Russia. *Polar Science* 101016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polar.2023.101016>

Matthes, H., Habeck, J.O., Horstkotte, T., Laptander, R., Istomin, K., Komu, T., Rasmus, S., Forbes, B.C., Eronen, J.T., Tømmervik, H. Translating practitioners' knowledge into climate modelling: from critical seasonal events in reindeer herding to climate indices. (manuscript)

Pekkarinen, A.-J. & Rasmus, S. (eds.) 2024. Poronhoidon varautuminen ja selviytymiskeinot uusiin, äkillisiin ja poikkeuksellisiin olosuhteisiin: POVAUS-hankkeen loppuraportti. *Luonnonvara- ja biotalouden tutkimus* 101/2024. Luonnonvarakeskus. Helsinki. 119 p.

Rasmus, S. & Laptander, R., Horstkotte, T., Habeck, J.O., Istomin, K., Komu, T., Matthes, H., Sarkki, S., Tømmervik, H., Forbes, B.C., Eronen, J.T. Rethinking adaptation in a rapidly changing Arctic. (manuscript)

Rasmus, S. & Sarkki, S., Wang, I., Burgess, P., Habeck, J.O., Horstkotte, T., Jokinen, M., Matthes, H., Mettiäinen, I., Parviainen, T., Pekkarinen, A., Post, L., Rikkonen, T., Sorvali, J., Turunen, M., Väärälä, T., Eronen, J.T. Playing with dreams: workshop tool

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

to support future-oriented work in communities and livelihoods. *The Polar Journal* (manuscript).

Rasmus, S., Turunen, M., Melamies, I., Väärälä, T., Komu, T. 2022. Naisen rooli porotaloudessa pysyy ja monipuolistuu. *Poromies* 4/2022

Rasmus, S., Pekkarinen, A., Jokinen, M., Kumpula, J., Landauer, M., Lehtonen, I., Mettiäinen, I., Sarkki, S., Sorvali, J., Turunen, M. ja Tuomenvirta, H. 2024. Parempaa polkua raivaamassa. *Poromies* 1/2024, 61-65.

Rasmus, S., Sarkki, S., Pekkarinen, A.-J., Jokinen, M., Mettiäinen, I., Post, L., Rikkonen, T., Sorvali, J., Väärälä, T. 2023a. Porotalouden tulevaisuus: unelmia ja yllätyksiä. CHARTER Working Paper 2. https://www.charter-arctic.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Porotalouden_tulevaisuus_tyopaja_-_Inari_raportti_221222_valmis.pdf

Rasmus, S., Sarkki, S., Pekkarinen, A.-J., Jokinen, M., Mettiäinen, I., Post, L., Rikkonen, T., Sorvali, J., Väärälä, T. 2023b. The Future of Reindeer Husbandry: Surprises and Dreams. A Workshop Summary Report. CHARTER Working Paper 3. <https://www.charter-arctic.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Reindeer-husbandry-dreams-and-surprises-report.pdf>

Sarkki, S & Rasmus, S., Pekkarinen, A., Jokinen, M., Mettiäinen, I., Parviainen, T., Post, L., Rikkonen, T., Sorvali, J., Väärälä, T., Habeck, J.O., Eronen, J.T. Adapting in polycrisis: Case of Arctic reindeer herding. *Globalizations* (submitted).

Sarkki, S. Pihlajamäki, M., Rasmus, S., Eronen, J. 2023. "Rights for Life" scenario to reach biodiversity targets and social equity for indigenous peoples and local communities. *Biological Conservation* 280 (Special Issue "The central importance of social justice in conservation science") 109958. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2023.109958>

Sarkki, S., Rasmus, S., Habeck, J. O., Matthes, H., Pihlajamäki, M., Eronen, J.T. Exploring the land-use futures around reindeer herding in Finland by "wild logic" -scenarios. *Journal of Land Use Science* (special issue "Sustainability Challenges in the Arctic: Exploring Land Use Changes and Their Impacts") (submitted, a)

Sarkki, S., Rasmus, S., Habeck, J.O., Matthes, H., Pihlajamäki, M., Eronen, J. Elaborating the SSP-based scenario architecture by concept of Governance Assumptions. *Land Use Policy* (submitted, b).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

Skarin, A., Turunen, M., Eilertsen, S.M., Rautiainen, H., Horstkotte, T., Baal, O.N.A., Blind, L.A., Emanuelsson, O., Hallergren, O., Kaddik, A.-M., Labba, L.-T., Larsson, H., Larsson, M., Lifjell, T., Lundgren, J., Majuri, K., Mustonen, J., Oskal, H., Paulsen, M., Post, L., Rasmus, S., Risvoll, C., Tømmervik, H., Utsi, N.-J., Vannar, E.N., Åhman, B. 2024. Vinterutfodring av renar - effekter på renarnas beteende, renskötseln och miljön. Rapport från en NKJ-workshop i Arvidsjaur 8–9 Juni 2022. Rangifer Report No. 18.

Turunen, M., Rasmus, S., Komu, T., Melamies, I., Väärälä, T., Inget, V.-P. Reindeer husbandry is more than herding – Contemporary roles of women in reindeer husbandry in Finland. *Journal of Rural Studies* (submitted).

Tømmervik, H. 2023. Report from the seminar/workshop in Plassjesne-Rossen tjjelte – Røros, Norway August 15th -16th 2023. CHARTER milestone 6 report (internal report).

Wang, I., Rasmus, S., Sarkki, S., Habeck, J.O., Burgess, P., Pekkarinen, A.-J., Eronen, J. 2023. Playing With Dreams - Workshop Playing Cards (openly accessible design process; workshop material and a guide for facilitating future-oriented workshop). Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8334154>

APPENDIX I

The herding game

v1.0

This game is to facilitate discussions about cumulative and compound pressures, holistic adaptation, resource needs, and the use of different knowledge sources in reindeer husbandry. The game enables sharing and comparing practical examples, give concrete examples of abstract things like “knowledge use” or “being supported by external resources”. The game considers at least two levels of needs and actions: the practical (individual, district) level, and the governance level of the livelihood; it can help to illustrate the differing views and needs.

Needed: gameboard (round), some tokens (resources), seasonal cards, surprise cards.

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Important seasonal events / conditions:

Summer pastures - calving – calf marking – hay making
Autumn pastures – rut – round-ups – slaughter - migration
Winter pastures – herding – feeding – predation
Spring pastures – migration – herding - feeding

Seasonal conditions cards:

Hot and dry summer; plenty of insects
Very wet summer; poor hay making conditions
Typical summer conditions (x2)

Typical autumn conditions
No mushroom
Late snow and ice formation
Early snow on unfrozen ground, molds and basal ice

Typical winter conditions
Long cold periods
Very deep snow
Heavy rain on snow, icy snow

Late snow melt & growing season start
Early snow melt & growing season start
Typical spring conditions (x2)

Surprise cards:

Land-use development and conflict [details? wind power, mine, etc.?
Wolves
Migration (inflow/outflow of people)
Epidemic in reindeer
Pandemic like COVID-19
Impacts of geopolitical tensions: high prices etc.; other market disturbances

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Tokens/resources:

Reaction tokens: green, yellow and red. Yellow and red means need to use some extra resources.

Annual resources (reindeer, herders, money, pastures/mobility, feed/feeding; teams will get some for each year, but need to define them themselves – in some cases resources might be minimal when it comes to pastures/mobility or feed/feeding).

Renewable resources (trust, knowledge, collaboration...)

Governance level resources (“Subsidies and compensations”)

Dynamics:

Players or teams selected; resources shared.

Season after season, conditions card (and possibly surprise cards) are randomly selected. After the card is picked, teams explain what this situation means for them; what actions and resources are needed.

-What is actually happening? What are the impacts? How do you realize this is happening? What do you need to know about it? Can you get that information? How and from whom?

-What needs to be done? What do you do yourself? What resources and knowledge you need? What would you need others (who?) to do – are external resources needed?

What others need to understand about districts, and herding, in certain difficult situations? How may their views differ (“what is the question”, when asked from various actors)? What is the knowledge different actors base their actions on? Whose knowledge is missing? What are the consequences of competing knowledge or lack of knowledge? For example, when impact assessments are made in land-use projects, what are the factors and topics that need to be considered so that the assessment truly reflects reindeer herders’ viewpoints?

See the “knowledge cards” below.

Events during previous seasons will impact the following ones – depending on the actions. Some resources are renewed after each herding year.

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The group can decide about competition, collaboration, and winning, as well as how long to play. Playing with current conditions, or with future conditions (probabilities) is possible. It is possible to include views, needs and knowledges of the governance level, or science, as well.

To get useful outcomes (“not just playing”):

Need to concentrate on discussion, not on the game. Game is only a way to facilitate the discussion.

Need to take notes and document the game.

Need to compare the actions, needs, possibilities between teams.

Need to remember there are different actors, in reality, like other land-users and their needs.

Need to look for transformative knowledge. In the best case, joint understanding on the situation (systems knowledge), and shared view on actions and needs in the situation (normative knowledge), can lead to actual change – knowledge that can change the way the land-use planning is carried out, or reindeer herding is managed (transformative knowledge).

Need to decide the next steps together – how to continue, where, when and with whom.

Need to report the lessons learnt to decision makers (policy relevance; policy recommendations) and to herding communities (local relevance).

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Knowledge cards (to be used as reminders and discussion openers)

CASE, SITUATION, EVENT

- extreme weather event
- extractive industry; impact assessment
- etc.

What do you need to know?
What others need to understand about reindeer herding?
What are the factors and topics that need to be considered so that herders' viewpoints are truly understood?
What is the knowledge base that is used / should be used?
What are the knowledge sources that are used / should be used?
Whose knowledge is missing?
What are the consequences of competing knowledge or lack of knowledge?

SYSTEMS KNOWLEDGE

What is actually happening, why, and is this a problem?

NORMATIVE KNOWLEDGE

What needs be done, by who, how, why?
What is the aim of these actions?

TRANSFORMATIVE KNOWLEDGE

Knowledge and learning leading to actual change
-within the livelihood
-how reindeer herding is managed
-land-use planning is carried out, etc.

PRESENT DAY vs FUTURE

What knowledge might be needed in the future?

PRESENT DAY vs FUTURE

Are actions and adaptations leading towards "desired future"?

PRESENT DAY vs PAST

How the knowledge of past generations can be used?
How the knowledge on past events and actions can be gained?

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Knowledge on ENVIRONMENT vs Knowledge on HUMAN BEINGS and COMMUNITIES? Or linkages between these?
TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE LOCAL KNOWLEDGE Indigenous knowledge Árbediehtu Experiential knowledge Practitioner knowledge, know-how, learning by doing
CITIZEN SCIENCE Local observations and experiences
SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE Observations Monitoring Data Research publications
Knowledge through EDUCATION and Guidance
Knowledge and perceptions in GOVERNANCE AND ADMINISTRATION (reindeer sector, other sectors, local, regional, national, international level)
KNOWLEDGE AND PERCEPTIONS OF HERDERS
Knowledge and perceptions of OTHER LAND-USERS AND LIVELIHOOD PRACTITIONERS

APPENDIX II – WP6 metadata

Please note that this table includes also events that have been organized jointly with WP3, and summarized earlier in WP3 deliverables.

APPENDIX II – WP6 metadata

Title/ Dataset	Event	Location	Time	Summa- rized in	Contri- butors	Collabo- rators	Creator	Creator's affiliation	Type of data	Description	Method	Keywords
Workshop notes, Kuusamo, 2021	Work- shop	Kuusamo, Finland	24.8. 2021	D3.3	LAY, UH	SUURPORO, POMURI, CLIMINI	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop	Climate change impacts on reindeer herding, predators, land use, cumulative impacts, Finland
Workshop notes, Rovaniemi, 2021	Work- shop	Rovaniemi, Finland	15.9. 2021	D3.3	LAY, UH	CLIMINI	Minna Turunen, Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes, photos	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop (female herders)	Operational environment of reindeer herding, desired futures, female herders, Finland
Workshop notes, Inari, 2022/1	Work- shop	Inari, Finland	30.3. 2022	D3.3	LAY, UH	NKJ- network, CLIMINI	Minna Turunen, Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes, photos	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop	Operational environment of reindeer herding, supplementary feeding of reindeer, Finland, Sápmi
Workshop notes, Rovaniemi, 2022/1	Work- shop	Rovaniemi, Finland	1.4. 2022	D3.3	LAY, UH, UHAM	POVAUS	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes, photos	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop, Surprises and dreams	Operational environment of reindeer herding, global drivers, desired futures, adaptation, young people, Finland
Meeting notes, Savukoski, 2022	Town- hall meeting	Savukoski, Finland	6.4. 2022	D3.3	UTU		Salla Eilola	University of Turku	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Meeting, open discussion	Environmental changes, municipality strategy, desired futures, local priorities, Finland, Savukoski
Workshop notes, Inari, 2022/2	Work- shop	Inari, Finland	3.5. 2022	D3.3	LAY, UH	CLIMINI	Minna Turunen, Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes, photos	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop (female herders)	Operational environment of reindeer herding, desired futures, female herders, Finland, Sápmi

Workshop notes, Inari, 2022/3	Workshop	Inari, Finland	4.5. 2022	D3.3	LAY, UH	POVAUS	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes, photos	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop, Surprises and dreams	Operational environment of reindeer herding, global drivers, desired futures, adaptation, young people, Finland, Sápmi
Workshop notes, Inari, 2022/4	Workshop	Inari, Finland	5.5. 2022	D3.3	LAY, UH	AROSS, CLIMINI	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Meeting, open discussion	Climate change impacts on reindeer herding, critical seasonal conditions, local observations, Finland, Sápmi
Meeting notes, Rovaniemi, 2022/2	Town-hall meeting	Rovaniemi, Finland	6.6. 2022	D3.3	LAY, UH	POVAUS	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of surprising developments listed by participants	Questionnaire survey to participants	Operational environment of reindeer herding, global drivers, surprises, Finland, Sápmi
Workshop notes, Arvidsjaur, 2022	Workshop	Arvidsjaur, Sweden	8.-9.6. 2022	D3.3	LAY, NINA, UmU	NKJ-network	Hans Tømmervik	NINA	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop	Operational environment of reindeer herding, supplementary feeding of reindeer, Finland, Norway, Sweden, Sápmi
Meeting notes, Inari, 2022/5	Briefing	Inari, Finland (and online)	9.6. 2022	D3.3	LAY, UH	AROSS, CLIMINI	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Meeting, open discussion	Climate change impacts on reindeer herding, critical seasonal conditions, climate model development, Finland, Sápmi
Workshop notes, Inari, 2022/6	Workshop	Inari, Finland	25.8. 2022	D3.7	LAY, UH	POVAUS	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop, Surprises and dreams	Operational environment of reindeer herding, global drivers, desired futures, adaptation, Finland, Sápmi

Workshop notes, Kuusamo, 2022	Workshop	Kuusamo, Finland	12.9. 2022	D3.7	LAY, UH	CLIMINI	Minna Turunen, Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes, photos	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop (female herders)	Operational environment of reindeer herding, desired futures, female herders, Finland
Meeting notes, Tromsø, 2023	World cafe	Tromsø, Norway	1.2. 2023	D6.5	LAY, UH	ArcticHubs, JUSTNORTH	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	World cafe discussions	environmental changes, land use policies, desired futures, reconciliation, justice, Arctic
Workshop notes, Rovaniemi, 2022/3	Workshop	Rovaniemi Finland	9.12. 2022	D3.7	LAY, UH	POVAUS	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop, Surprises and dreams	Operational environment of reindeer herding, global drivers, desired futures, adaptation, Finland
Workshop notes, Savukoski, 2023	Workshop	Savukoski, Finland	13.4. 2023	D3.7	LAY, UH, UTU		Salla Eilola	University of Turku	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop	Operationalizing the municipality strategy, blind spots in the strategy, local priorities, Finland, Savukoski
Workshop notes, Tuorpon, 2023	Workshop	Jokkmokk, Sweden	14.8. 2023	D3.7	UmU	ArcticHubs	Tim Horstkotte	Umeå University	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop, Surprises and dreams	Operational environment of reindeer herding, global drivers, desired futures, adaptation, Sweden, Sápmi, Tuorpon
Workshop notes, Sirges, 2023	Workshop	Jokkmokk, Sweden	15.8. 2023	D3.7	UmU	ArcticHubs	Tim Horstkotte	Umeå University	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop, Surprises and dreams	Operational environment of reindeer herding, global drivers, desired futures, adaptation, Sweden, Sápmi, Sirges
Workshop notes, Jåhkågaska 2023	Workshop	Jokkmokk, Sweden	17.8. 2023	D3.7	UmU	ArcticHubs	Tim Horstkotte	Umeå University	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop, Surprises and dreams	Operational environment of reindeer herding, global drivers, desired futures, adaptation, Sweden,

												Sápmi, Jåhkågaska tjiellde
Workshop notes, Røros, 2023	Workshop	Plaassjan/Røros, Norway	15.-16.8. 2023	D3.7	LAY, NINA, UHAM		Hans Tømmervik	NINA	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop, walking workshop	Operational environment of reindeer herding, pasture conditions, Norway, Plaassjan/Røros
Workshop notes, Rovaniemi 2023/1	Workshop	Rovaniemi Finland	30.8. 2023	D3.7	AWI, LAY, UH		Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop	Climate change impacts on reindeer herding, critical seasonal conditions, climate model development, Finland, Sápmi
Workshop notes, Rovaniemi 2023/2	Workshop	Rovaniemi Finland	13.11. 2023	D3.7	LAY, UH	POVAUS	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop	Operational environment of reindeer herding, global drivers, desired futures, adaptation, Finland
Meeting notes, Espoo 2024	World cafe	Espoo, Finland	10.6. 2024	D6.5	LAY, UH	ArcicHubs	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	World cafe discussions	Sustainable development, resilient futures, Arctic, reindeer herding, tourism, forestry, desired futures
Workshop notes, Helsinki 2024	Workshop	Helsinki, Finland	12.6. 2024	D6.5	AWI, LAY, UH		Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Researcher workshop	Operational environment of reindeer herding, critical seasonal conditions, climate model development, knowledge systems, Finland, Sápmi
Workshop notes, Ylläs, 2024	Workshop	Ylläs, Finland	26.-27.8. 2024	D6.5	AWI, LAY, UH, UHAM	LANDPATHS	Sirpa Rasmus	University of Lapland	notes	Detailed notes of group discussions	Participatory workshop	Cumulative impacts on reindeer herding, climate change, land-use, governance, knowledge systems, Finland, Norway, Sweden, Sápmi